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Research Article

THE COMPARISON OF THE LEVEL OF CREATININE AND CYSTATIN C FOR THE INDICATION OF EARLY-STAGE DIABETIC NEPHROPATHY TO SCREEN OUT DIABETIC PATIENTS

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Abstract:

***Objective:** The aim of our study was to compare the level of creatinine and cystatin C for the indication of early-stage diabetic nephropathy to screen out diabetic patients.*

***Study Design:** A cross-sectional study.*

***Place and Duration:** This study was conducted at Services hospital Lahore for the duration of one year starting from October, 2019 to September, 2020.*

***Methodology:** In our study we selected 154 subjects from which 77 healthy subjects were in control group and 77 patients of diabetes were in patient group, and their age range was more than 18 years. We use IMAGIN Specific Protein Analyzer to measure the level of creatinine and serum cystatin C. Standardized laboratory protocols were applied to carry out both tests. SPSS version 20 for the analysis of data. The results of study were determined in terms of detection of diabetic nephropathy which were finalized on albuminuria status basis and categorized in three groups: microalbuminuria, normoalbuminuria and macroalbuminuria.*

***Results:** In our present study we selected 154 subjects. According to gender distribution the number females were 41.6% and the number of males were 58.4%, and they were equally distributed in control and patient group. As compared to control and normoalbuminuria groups the level of creatinine (1.0 ± 0.13 mg/dl) and level of Cystatin C (4.7 ± 3.9 mg/dl) were significantly found high in macroalbuminuric group.*

***Conclusion:** At the end of our study, we conclude that serum cystatin C is a significant predictive marker of diabetic nephropathy than serum creatinine.*

Key Words: Serum Creatinine, Diabetic Nephropathy, Serum Cystatin C

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INTRODUCTION:

Type 2 diabetes is on a continuous rise worldwide owing to a steady increase in obese and aging population. The global prevalence of diabetes was estimated at 171 million (2.8%) in the year 2000 which is expected to reach 366 million 4.4% figure by the year 2030 [1]. The current prevalence of diabetes in Pakistan is around 10.0% [2]. As per WHO estimates, Pakistan is ranked 7th largest country suffering from diabetes mellitus and it is expected that by 2030 this rank will climb the ladder to 4th position which is an alarming statistics and situation [3]. Diabetic nephropathy is one of the most common complications of diabetes. Diabetic nephropathy by definition is macroalbuminuria (albumin excretion rate > 300 mg /24 hours) and deteriorating renal function is a known fact in diabetics. Previous reports confirm that approximately one third to one half of diabetic patients develop renal complications [4]. Albuminuria is a significant prognostic factor for risk stratification of diabetic nephropathy and monitoring of its progression.

There was a belief that microalbuminuria is predictive of future overt diabetic nephropathy in 80% cases, however, on the contrary, it has been proposed that around 30% of microalbuminuria cases progress to overt nephropathy after 10 years follow-up [4]. Presently, the phenomena of normoalbuminuria diabetic nephropathy are well established and portrays that diabetic patients may present with a decreased GFR without progression from normal to microalbuminuria. Gold standard method for determining GFR in research settings are inulin and Cr-EDTA plasma clearance. These techniques are time consuming, laborious and requiring expertise making them unfit for clinical practice. Hence the used index for GFR is serum creatinine (mg/dl). Moreover, its sensitivity is poor in early renal damage and by the time its levels are detectable, significant decrease in GFR has already occurred [5].

Putting these facts together, there is a ground for identification of alternative biomarkers to predict diabetic nephropathy early so that timely management and maintenance can be exercised. Cystatin C a 13.3k Da plasma protein is relatively new marker in the prediction of renal impairment and it correlates positively with other renal tests like GFR. Serum creatinine also a proven marker of nephropathy is relatively weaker test and easily changes by different maneuvers and circumstances like a person's muscle mass [5]. Cystatin C has been found constant and unaffected and an alternative with high sensitivity for diabetic nephropathy using a cut off of >60 ml of GFR

[6]. The focus of research by endocrinologists and other investigators is to find out new and better biomarkers for the diagnosis of early diabetic nephropathy. The aim of the study was to compare cystatin C and creatinine in the screening of diabetic patients on risk of early-stage diabetic nephropathy.

METHODOLOGY:

This cross-sectional study was conducted at Services hospital Lahore for the duration of one year starting from October, 2019 to September, 2020. A measured study sample of 77 diagnosed cases of diabetes were enrolled along with 77 normal controls. Convenient sampling technique was utilized. The study was conducted after obtaining permission from ethical review committee. A written informed consent was taken from all the patients. Demographic data was collected via questionnaires. 77 diabetes cases and 77 non-diabetics of both genders and adults age (above 18 years) were included in the study. For study purpose, Albuminuria was divided into three standard operational groups; I) Normoalbuminuria with ACR < 30mg/day, II) Microalbuminuria with ACR 30 to < 300mg/day and III) Macroalbuminuria with ACR > 300mg/day. Blood was drawn from peripheral veins, transferred to EDTA tube, gently mixed and made to stand upright. The blood samples were centrifuged at 2200 RPM for 10 minutes. The separated serum was stored at -20°C till completion of sample collection.

The urine samples were collected in the jars provided to the patients and centrifuged at 1000 RPM for 10 mins, these were also stored at -20°C till analysis. The estimation of cystatin C levels (mg/l) was carried out on IMAGIN Specific Protein Analyzer for quantitative determination of human cystatin C in serum. Similarly, the estimation of urinary albumin levels was carried out on IMAGIN Specific Protein Analyzer for quantitative determination of human Microalbumin [MALB] in urine by immunoturbidimetry. Data was analyzed using SPSS 20.0 version. First, descriptive statistics was applied to measure frequency and percentages for categorical variables like gender, and mean and standard deviations for continuous variables. Secondly, using student's t-test the means and standard deviation levels of serum cystatin C, serum creatinine and clinical measurements of blood pressure were compared among patients and controls. Categories of albuminuria were created as per operational definitions.

The mean levels of serum cystatin C and creatinine were compared among these categories using T-test. For further analysis the renal status glomerular filtration (GFR) rate was categorized as GFR < 60,

GFR 60-89.9 and GFR > 90 [7]. A p-value of <0.05 was considered significant difference. Parametric tests were applied as majority of the continuous numerical data was found equally distributed and dispersed.

In our present study we selected 154 patients according to gender distribution the number females were 41.6% and the number of males were 58.4%, and they were equally distributed in control and patient group. (Table 01).

RESULTS:

Table No 01: Gender Distribution

Gender	Patients		Control		p-value
	Qty	%age	Qty	%age	
Males	45	58.4%	45	58.4%	0.51
Females	32	41.6%	32	41.6%	
Total	77	100%	77	100%	

The urinary albumin and creatinine were analyzed and it was found that there were 15 (19.4%) normoalbuminuric, 53 (68.8%) microalbuminuria and 9 (11.6%) cases with macroalbuminuric (Table 02).

Table No 02: Analysis of Creatinine and Urinary Albumin

Urinary Albumin	Qty	%age
Normoalbuminuric	15	19.5%
Microalbuminuria	53	68.8%
Macroalbuminuric	9	11.7%
Total	77	100%

There was a gradual increasing trend of age and urinary albumin in the study subjects. The mean age of macroalbuminuric (59.3 ± 5.5 years) cases was significantly higher than controls (55.5 ± 5.1) and rest of albumin categories i.e., normoalbuminuric (56.2 ± 5.4) and microalbuminuria (56.5 ± 5.4). Male gender was predominant in

the study and also in all albumin categories and controls, however, they were not significantly different among categories (p-value, 0.58). (Table 03).

Table 03: Association of Age and Gender with Urine Albumin Status of Patients and Controls

Age	Control	Diabetic Patients			p-value
		Normaloalbuminuric	Microalbuminuric	Macroalbuminuric	
Mean±S.D	55.7±5.1	56.2±5.9	56.5±5.4	59.3±5.5	<0.001
Gender					
Male	45(58.4%)	8(53.3%)	31(58.5%)	6(66.6%)	0.58
Female	32(41.6%)	7(46.7%)	22(41.5%)	3(33.3%)	

A selective analysis of cystatin C and serum creatinine levels was done according to GFR categories. The mean cystatin C was significantly high (1.7 ± 1.2) in patients with moderate to high kidney damage (GFR < 60), and mean cystatin C was also very high (2.6 ± 2.4) in patients with mild kidney damage (GFR 60-89). Serum creatinine was also found significantly deranged (1.2 ± 0.21) in GFR < 60 category, whereas in GFR 60-89 it was found border line deranged (0.94 ± 0.11). (Table IV).

Table No 04: Relationship of Cystatin C and Creatinine with GFR Categories

Parameters	GFR<60(n=04)	GFR 60.89(n=57)	GFR≥(n=16)	P-value
Cystatin C	1.7±1.2	2.6±2.4	1.2±0.9	<0.001
Creatinine	1.2±0.21	0.94±0.11	0.70±0.18	

DISCUSSION:

The study findings reveal that cystatin C is significantly raised than creatinine in not only macroalbuminuria but also in cases of microalbuminuria. Microalbuminuria is most prevalent in the study, showing that two-third of patients were in the process of development of early diabetic nephropathy. Our study findings of raised cystatin C in early nephropathic derangement validate many previous reports on the topic. Lee BW witnessed that serum cystatin C is significantly lower in normoalbuminurics (0.83 ± 0.22) than in microalbuminurics and macroalbuminurics (0.94 ± 0.33 and 1.05 ± 0.28 respectively; $p < 0.001$) [7]. Jeon YK also witnessed a similar trend of relationship of cystatin C and diabetic nephropathy (micro and macroalbuminuric) [8,9,10]. Similarly, in the current study the average serum creatinine and cystatin C are found high in micro and macroalbuminuric cases. Most of the study patients were in the early stage of diabetic nephropathy, however, 11.6% were proven cases of diabetic nephropathy (ACR > 300 mg/dl). Cystatin C was found significantly high in micro and microalbumin categories. Though serum creatinine

was also found deranged in these cases, it is not that distinctive than cystatin C.

Previous literature on cystatin C suggests its superiority in detecting early diabetic nephropathy [11]. As patients on the risk of diabetic nephropathy can be recovered and early deterioration of renal function can be averted. This highlights the significance of an easy and feasible laboratory parameter like cystatin C [4,9,12]. Serum cystatin C has proven its role as an alternative marker for estimating GFR. Moreover, the failure of creatinine to detect early decline in GFR is due to the fact that serum creatinine levels only start rising when almost 50% of renal function is lost, suggesting that GFR can change before serum creatinine becomes abnormal [13,14]. Cystatin C may rise faster than creatinine after a fall in GFR and is a reliable endogenous marker for assessing renal function in type 2 diabetic patients with renal impairment [15,16]. It was found out that cystatin C and creatinine are significantly high in moderate to severe kidney damage and it is also high in mild kidney damage category (GFR 60-89). Our results have time and again proven that cystatin C was a highly useful marker of kidney damage in diabetic

patients. There are many advantages of the study which include; firstly, it was a comparative study comprising of diabetics and control groups, with a reasonable sample of 77 cases and 77 controls. Relationship of two commonly used markers i.e., cystatin C and serum creatinine were compared according to patient's albuminuria status and then also according to GFR status.

CONCLUSION:

At the end of our study, we conclude that serum cystatin C is a significant predictive marker of diabetic nephropathy than serum creatinine.

REFERENCES:

1. Harjutsalo V, Groop PH. Epidemiology and risk factors for diabetic kidney disease. *Adv Chronic Kidney Dis.* 2014; 21: 260-6.
2. Engelgau MM, El-Saharty S, Kudesia P, Rajan V, Rosenhouse PS, Okamoto K. Capitalizing on the demographic transition: tackling non communicable diseases in South Asia, World Bank. Washington DC. 2011.
3. Akter S, Rahman MM, Abe SK, Sultana P. Prevalence of diabetes and prediabetes and their risk factors among Bangladeshi adults: a nationwide. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization.* 2014; 92: 204-13.
4. Fiseha T. Urinary biomarkers for early diabetic nephropathy in type 2 diabetic patients *Bio mark Res.* 2015; 3: 16.
5. Assal HS, Tawfeek S, Rasheed EA, El-Lebedy D, Thabet EH. Serum Cystatin C and Tubular Urinary Enzymes as Biomarkers of Renal Dysfunction in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. *Clin Med Insights Endocrinol Diabetes.* 2013; 6: 7–13.
6. Tesch G, Amur S, Schousboe JT, Siegel JN, Lesko LJ, Bai JP. Successes achieved and challenges ahead in translating biomarkers into clinical applications. *AAPS J.* 2012; 12: 24353.
7. Lee BW, Ihm SH, Choi MG, Yoo H J. The comparison of cystatin C and creatinine as an accurate serum marker in the prediction of type 2 diabetic nephropathy. *Diabetes Research and Clinical Practice.* 2017; 78: 428–34.
8. Jeon YK, Kim MR, Huh JE. Cystatin C as an Early Biomarker of Nephropathy in Patients with Type 2 Diabetes. *J Korean Med Sci.* 2012; 26: 258-63.
9. Kitabchi AE, Umpierrez GE, Miles JM, Fisher JN. Hyperglycemic crises in adult patients with diabetes. *Diabetes Care.* 2016; 32: 1335–43.
10. Pavkov ME, Knowler WC, Hanson RL, Williams DE, Lemley KV, Myers BD, et al. Comparison of Serum Cystatin C, Serum Creatinine, Measured GFR, and Estimated GFR to Assess the Risk of Kidney Failure in American Indians With Diabetic Nephropathy. *Am J Kidney Dis.* 2013; 62: 33–41.
11. Ferguson MA, Waikar SS. Established and emerging markers of kidney function. *Clin Chem.* 2012; 58: 680-9.
12. Domingueti CP, Fóscolo RB, Silva ACS, Dusse LMS, Reis JS, Carvalho MG, et al. Evaluation of creatinine-based and cystatin C-based equations for estimation of glomerular filtration rate in type 1 diabetic patients. *Arch Endocrinol Metab.* 2016; 60: 108-16.
13. Hamed EO, Zaky NA, Kamal YM. Simple cystatin-C formula for estimation of glomerular filtration rate in chronic kidney disease in diabetic patients. *AAMJ.* 2016; 9: 81–9.
14. Mussap M, Vestra MD, Fioretto P, Saller A, Varagnolo M. Cystatin C is a more sensitive marker than creatinine for the estimation of GFR in type 2 diabetic patients. *Kidney Int.* 2012; 61: 1453-61.
15. Shera AS, Jawad F, Maqsood A, Jamal S, Azfar M, Ahmed U. Prevalence of Chronic Complications and Associated Factors in Type 2 Diabetes. *J Pak Med Assoc.* 2014; 54: 54-9.
16. Sohail M. Prevalence of Diabetic Retinopathy among Type 2 Diabetes Patients in Pakistan – Vision Registry. *Pak J Ophthalmol.* 2014; 30: 204-12.